

Influence of Capacity Building on Job Performance of Academic Staff of Tertiary Institutions in Imo State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of capacity building on job performance of academic staff of tertiary institutions in Imo State. This study adopted a survey design with three research questions and three hypotheses. The population for the study was drawn from the four tertiary institutions mentioned above with a total number of three thousand one hundred and eight five (3,185) academic staff. The sample size for this study was four hundred (400) academic staff. Simple random sampling technique was used to obtain the sample size for the study. Data collecting instrument was titled Capacity Building and Job Performance of Academic Staff Questionnaire which was subjected to content validity by three experts including the research supervisor. Analysis of data were done using the mean and ground mean for research questions, while t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The result of finding was also discussed based on the responses from the variables used for the study. Finding reveals that academics staff stands on high extent to all the variable. Based on this the following recommendation were made: The practice of favoritism should be abolished and training or capacity building programme of all sort distributed equitably according to the need of both the individual(s) and the institutions, Academic staff capacity building must be thought of as a long-term process, which begins with initial preparation and only ends when the academic staff retires from the profession. There should be new approach to the education and development of academic staff, which requires a transformation of process and policies that support academic staff, their education, their work and their growth in the profession. Academic staff, capacity building must be systematically planned, supported, funded and researched to guarantee the effectiveness of this process.

Keyword: Capacity Building, Job Performance, Distant Learning, Workshops Collaboration Studies

INTRODUCTION

The acquisition of new body of skill and knowledge has been a sine-qua-non for academic excellence in institutions of higher learning. Darling (2018) noted that "knowledge is the basis for permission to practice and for decisions that are made with respect to the unique needs of the clients". Bolam, (Tony, 2020) remarked that "the ultimate aim of staff capacity building is to improve the quality of teaching and learning. The immediate aim is to improve the efficiency of those with teaching responsibility".

The Nigerian educational system like any other system across the globe is a dynamic organization facing challenges of scientific/technological modifications at all time, social and cultural influences. The educational system of Nigeria over the years has been on decline, with strange event ranging from examination malpractice, cultism, academic decay to unavailability of teaching and learning aids, incessant lecturers strike actions, poor result of students' in both internal and external examinations etc (Darling, 2018). In the light of these ugly events, an effective and efficient work force becomes necessary to perform specific assignments in the midst of these challenges for the

achievement of the desired educational goals. To realize this aim, the tertiary institutions provide their work force academic staff or lecturers with adequate enhancement (development) opportunities and suitable facilities at their various fields of study to correct the abnormalities and imbalance in the system.

Cole, (2016) remarked that if any organization including the tertiary institutions takes the development of her academic staff seriously and establishes a deliberate and systematic policy of academic staff capacity building, members of staff who benefit from such training program would be committed and will remain on the job for a long time in the organization; it is not enough for an organization to increase the number of workers in its effort to increase quality of product but must also remember to make those existing ones, at every level more efficient by consistently exposing them to continuous learning process by create room for in-servicing training within and outside the state as the case may be. Also it is not good enough to solely rely on the past skills and knowledge acquired by the academic staff but important to expose them to current skills, knowledge etc. That are prevalent in recent time and useful in solving complex problems. This enhancement of ability may be provided formally or informally (Darling, 2018). The formal type is obtained through attendance of institutions of higher learning and knowledge which is acquired through teaching for the award of certificate, other examples include conferences, consultation teaching, booster courses, extension courses, long vacation study, training in computer technology (ICT), collaboration studies, workshops, orientation programmes, seminars, internship arrangements all this capacity building can take place within and outside the state. The informal activities of capacity building includes; participation in professional associations, reading of professional books (Journals, newspapers) listening and watching electronic media.

Significance of the Study

The role of academic staff capacity building in enhancing our educational system can never be over emphasized. This empirical study will therefore be of immense value to educational administrators in general academic managers in particular in providing capacity building policies that will enhance the efficiency of academic staff in tertiary institution and promote job performance and effectiveness in state higher institutions. The study will also be relevant to the central educational ministry especially in matching curriculum innovations and educational policy formulation with career academic staff development, bearing in mind that the career academic staff finally converts these curriculum changes and educational policies to desired outcome in the life of the students.

The study will in no less measure be significant to practicing lecturers in developing the skill and ability to manage associated problems of student's diversity and taking full control of activities within and outside and other academic related matter as the case may be. In the same vein, it will offer a good opportunity to academic staff in tertiary institutions to undergo training on management of internal pressure in the university environment. This pressures include students' unwillingness to learn, examination malpractice, adverse students' population, teaching methodology etc. Moreover, the output to the society will also contribute to nation development as a result of its positive impact to the graduating students from the tertiary institutions in the state. Researchers, in the field of education management will benefit from the outcome of the study because the result of the study will provide an information for the conduct of other research work on time management and personal development of non-academic staff at various levels of education.

Theoretical Framework (Dreyfus and Dreyfus Theory)

The Dreyfus brothers' model of skill acquisition has attracted considerable interest in professional education. In their book, *Mind over machine*, the power of human intuition and expertise in the era of the computer (2016) revealed that their theory was first developed as an attack on the claims made by experts on artificial intuition before becoming a more broadly based theory of expertise.

Dreyfus described their model as depicting five stages of skill acquisition, the stage that teachers traverse as they mature from being novice to experts. This is helpful model, as it describes the professional and personal needs teachers have as they progress through this cycle. Their model is as follows: State One: Novice level (student teachers and first-year teachers). In this stage, teachers feel that practical personal experience is more valuable than information transmitted verbally. Teachers in this novice stage are taught the meaning of certain common terms and concepts, the rules of the school culture, and objective facts and features of situations. Some features prominent in this stage are, rigid adherence to taught rules, little situational perception and no discretionary judgement.

Stage Two: Advanced beginner level (second and third-year teachers). Once the novice has acquired some experience, he or she becomes an advanced beginner. Experience begins to affect behaviour in a meaningful way, at this stage, as the academic staff begin to combine their textbook knowledge with their experience knowledge (Eisenhart and Jones, 2022). In this stage, however, the academic staff are still submitting to hierarchical superiors and are not feeling a sense of autonomy regarding their jobs. This lack of personal agency also means that academic staff do not take full responsibility for their actions some features of this stage include; guidelines for action based on attributes or aspects of situations recognizable only after some prior experience, situational perception still limited and all attributes and aspects are treated separately and given equal importance.

Stage Three: Competent level (third and fourth year). Most advanced beginners move into this stage once they have enough experience and motivation to succeed. However, there is evidence that shows that some academic staff remain at a less-than-competent level of performance of efficiency in their job (Eisenhart and Jones, 2022). The two most important characteristics of teachers at this stage are: that they make conscious decisions about what they are going to do (plan, objectives, etc.), and that as they implement their plans, they can determine what is and is not important. In way academic staff have much more control over the situation, as they can organize themselves their daily activities and teaching practices.

Level 4 Proficient Stage: At this stage the follow task are being executed:

- See situations holistically rather than in terms of aspects
- See what is most important in a situation and tackle it.
- Perceives deviations from the normal pattern and improved in the current idea.
- Decision-making less labored
- Uses maxims for guidance whose meaning varies according to the situation.

Level 5 Expert

- No longer relies on rules guidelines or maxims
- Intuitive grasp of situation based on deep tacit understanding
- Analytic approaches used only in move situation or when proper section
- Vision of what is possible and go for it.

Distant Learning or Correspondence programme

Distance education was defined by Jegede (2020) as the provision of education by a mode other than the conventional face-to-face method but whose goals are similar to and just as noble and practical as those of on campus full time; face to face education. The characteristic of distance education was noted by Kegan (2016) in Jegede (2020) to include quasi separation of academic staff and learner.

The history of distance education dates back 1928 when Calab Philips of Boston USA started Distance education by teaching a business education course, shoot-hand by post. The hitherto declining trend in distance education in Nigeria especially in the early 90s is probably partly, associated with the decline in the effectiveness of the postal system (Agburuga, 2022) he continued that the correspondence method is the dominant mode. But now with enough network services distance

education could be a lot easier. Between 1933 and 1978, various forms of distance education programs were available in Nigeria. There were the correspondence study programmes of Rapid Results College, Wolsey Hall and Benneth College. The University of Lagos correspondence and open studies (COSH) programme started in 1974 but gradually is being transformed into a sandwich/part-time programme. The mode of delivery of distance education has undergone tremendous change at the global level. Beginning with the print intended purposely for correspondence education, the delivery of education to remote students has gone through the multimedia model, the Tele-learning model and now the emerging, fourth-generation of distance education, the flexible learning model (Jegede, 2020).

Personal Capacity Building

This is defined in terms of enhancing the talents, expanding the interest, improving the competence, and otherwise facilitating the professional and personal growth of academic staff particularly as instructor" (Gaff, 2015). Unlike the instructional component of professional development, which directly relates to master of subject and the delivery system, the personal development components focuses more on the need for academic staff to reflect upon their personal feelings, attitudes, values competencies, and limitations as professional personal development of lecturers emphasizes both the adult development perspective and the human resources development approach. The capacity building app views the academic staff as adults facing constant transitions in their careers and personal lives and needing assistance or support to learn and overcome professional and individual anxieties. On the other hand, the human resource development approach highlights the changing roles of academic staff career patterns and the need for academic staff to be constantly educated and trained for life-long career mobility within the academe and between academic and non-academic jobs (Toombs, 2023).

Several research findings have revealed the academic staff greater interest in decisions and activities that satisfies her personal needs and less attention to that, which concerns the instructional. However, academic staff should be assisted in their personal and professional development, since they are directly related to their teaching-learning function. Academic staff performance and vitality can be better enhanced within an environment that provides assistance to the faculty members to grow as professional human resources through a combination of supports and self-renewal efforts (Uwalaka, 2016).

Workshops and Training

The previous discussion has focused primarily on professional development current academic staff. However, if tomorrow's schools are going to be substantially different from the one we currently have, it is equally important to alter the preparation of future academic staff and administrators, hi fact, many have suggested that, with the large number of academic staff and administrators in tertiary institutions may likely to retire within the next ten years, changing the preparation of the incoming academic staff may have a greater and long lasting impact on altering the character of schooling than workshop programs for current staff, (Warwick and Reimners, 2015) opined that these programmes that help academic staff expectations, perspectives, all attitude about their future roles and responsibilities as well as about the students the teach, and the type of environments in which they will work.

Equally important, these preparation programs also provide the knowledge, experiences and skills that provide the foundation upon which subsequent expertise can be developed. Improving the quality and content of workshop programs will result in having educator who are ready and willing to respond to the challenges of restructuring school to meet the need of the students and the large society.

Collaboration Studies

Abali, (2023) similar to that of other professions, the continuing growth and professional development of educator may be substantially enhanced by opportunities to collaboration studies with others. The opportunity to take advantage of the expertise of others, and be recognized for their own, can provide educator with important reinforcement and incentive for continuing growth and development as well as the enhanced personal status and respect that comes from membership in a "community of learners" with their professional colleagues.

According to Eraut (2015), three complementary rationales have been used to explain the importance of collaboration studies among academic staff. One is human resources development, the second is the management of planned change, and the third is based on self-development by schools and lecturers. In regard to human resource development, there are two main concerns: to have enough personnel who are adequately prepared; and to maximize the preparation of anyone working in the system.

In regard to the second rationale, it is in the interest of the system of prepare the personnel who will implement any planned change. In other words, to enable education system to be reformed academic staff act not only as subjects, but also as objects of that reform (Uwalaka, 2016). Finally, the rational of self-development based three factors: it is believed mat institution and academic staff will be more likely to commit themselves to change when they have initiated the change themselves; this change is more likely to become institutionalized when academic staff are better prepared to plan and implement it; and needs and priorities will be identified more effectively at the local level, and thus the plan to change will respond to realistic professional development.

Statement of the Problem

There is one problem closely linked with the concept of manpower training and development vis-via capacity building in the educational sector and the economy of this nation, and that is the influence of training on employee efficiency. The interplay between these two concepts Shanker, (2020) broadened the realm of training and development by stating that "the earlier view of training and development was that people must receive education and acquire professional skills in higher schools or colleges that lasts throughout their careers, in other to overcome problems like: curricula of poor quality, too much emphasis on theory and little or none on practical learning, inadequate administrative skills in the system etc. Beach, (2015) claimed that general education is broader in scope while training has a more immediate utilization. He went further to state that "capacity building programs such as distant learning program, workshops, collaborations, studies etc. plays a large role in determining the effectiveness and efficiency of the academic staff. Research conducted on the failure of university educational policy showed that the necessary good conditions of service of academic staff including provision for lecturers' distant learning program, workshops etc, as a capacity building program were far from being realized (Okebukola, 2015).

In recent time, there- have been several complains on the decline of education across the nation. To localize and find a lasting solution to this problem the government has sought to revitalize the administrative structure of its educational system and has reiterated the need for effective allocation of resources for instructional development activities, design and implementation of curriculum relevant to the needs of the institutions and society. The extent at which these programme and actions have been implemented remain questionable since its influence in turning the wheel of progress in our tertiary institutions sector has been slow and chains of complains on the decline of education standard due to lecturers professional retrogression kept re-echoing.

Purpose of the Study

The primary purpose of this study is to identify and measure the relationship between capacity building and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Imo State. The study specifically sought to establish the following objectives:

1. To find out the level of distant learning program at the disposal of academic staff in tertiary institutions.
2. To find out the content of workshops training received by academic staff in tertiary institutions.
3. To find out the level of attendance of collaboration studies by academic staff in tertiary institutions.

Research Questions

In order to guide this study, the following research questions were posed.

1. To what extent does academic staff in tertiary institutions benefits from distant learning as a capacity building program?
2. To what extent does academic staff in tertiary institutions are aware of the availability of workshops as a capacity building program?
3. To what extent does academic staff level of attendance of collaboration studies contributes to their productivity and effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in the conduct of this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between distant learning program and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Imo State.
2. There is no significant relationship between workshops and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions.
3. There is no significant relationship between collaboration studies and job -performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research design adopted for this study was purely a survey research design. The study was carried out among academic staff in tertiary institutions in Imo State. The population of the study was (3,185) academic staff in four tertiary institutions in the state. Three research questions were posed and three hypotheses formulated to guide the study. A sample size of 400 academic staff was drawn from the total population. The random sampling techniques was adopted in selecting the simple size. The instrument for the research was a self-structured Questionnaire tagged "Capacity Building and Job performance of Academic Staff Questionnaires" (CABJPASQ). The questionnaire was divided into two sections: ("A" and "B". Section "A" elicited responses on the personal data of the respondents while, section "B" Measured Influence of Capacity Building on Job Performance of Academic Staff. Responses on the Questionnaire, were anchored on a five point inference scale based on the following decision rule: Very High Extent (VHE) 5, High Extent (HE) 4, Moderate Extent (ME) 3, Low Extent (LE) 2 and very low Extent (VLE) 1. The Questionnaire was validated by two experts and one other expert m the field of Educational Management and planning. The reliability of the instrument was tested using the test-re-test method. The responses of the two tests were computed using the Cronbach Alpha Statistical technique and a Coefficient Value of 0.87 was obtained to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions and analyzed the data while, the T-test statistics tools was employed to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. Any mean score of 3.0 and above was considered "High Extent" while means scores below 2.5 were considered "Low Extent"

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What Extent does Academic Staff in Tertiary Institution benefits from Distant Learning Programmes?

Table 1: Mean Scale of Respondents on the Extent to which Academic Staff in Tertiary Institutions Benefits from Distant Learning Programme

S/N	Items	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	%	SD	\bar{X}	Decision
1.	Academic staff who have been involved in distant learning programme share ideas/decision making with other academic staff.	250	100	30	20	-	85	0.1	4.3	HE
2.	There is enthusiasm in them that they have gone for staff development such as distant learning programme.	300	50	50	-	-	90	0.1	4.5	VHE
3.	They get involved with the organization of co-curriculum activities for students.	150	200	20	30	-	82	0.2	4.2	HE
4.	Academic staff portray some characteristics of self-development in their areas of profession as a result of distant learning programme.	50	200	30	10	10	61	0.2	3.0	HE

Table 1: showed that respondents in items 1, 3 and 4 with 85% (4.3), 82% (4.2) and 85% (4.3) are high extent which means that the scores were accepted, in the same vain, item 2 also recorded 90% (4.5) which is very high extent. Based on the decision level, it is clear that academic staff actually confirm that distant learning as a capacity building programme positively influence the professional development of academic staff in tertiary institutions.

Research Question 2: What Extent does Academic Staff in Tertiary Institutions are Aware of the Available Workshop as a capacity building programme?

Table 2: Mean Scale of Respondents on the Extent to which Academic Staff in Tertiary Institution are aware of Availability Workshops as a Capacity Building Programme

S/N	Items	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	%	SD	\bar{X}	Decision
5.	Academic staff are not available in all the institution to attend workshops and conferences.	50	250	50	30	20	61	0.2	3.0	ME
6.	Non-governmental organizations find it difficult to organize workshops for academic staff in tertiary institution.	60	240	50	50	-	64	0.3	3.2	ME
7.	Workshops are one of the capacity building programme that paves way for job performance.	150	100	100	30	20	80	0.4	4.1	HE

8.	Most times, organizers of these workshops are the National University Commission.	200	100	50	20	30	8.3	0.3	4.3	HE
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Table 2 reveals that the academic staff means scale in items of and 8 was 80% and 83% with (1) and 3) respectively showing high extent of the variable. This implies that academic staff in tertiary institutions upheld the high extent as regards to workshops as capacity building programme that can assist in improving academic staff job performance in tertiary institutions.

Research Question 3: What Extent does Academic Staff Level of Attendance of Collaboration Studies Contributes to their Productivity and Effectiveness in Tertiary Institutions?

Table 3: Mean Scale of Respondent on the Extent to which Academic Staff Level of Attendance on Collaboration Studies Contributes to their Productivity and Effectiveness.

S/N	Items	VHE	HE	ME	LE	VLE	%	SD	\bar{X}	Decision
9.	Academic staff get much involved in courses like evaluation techniques in schools administration and administrative law.	250	100	50	-	-	90	0.1	4.5	VHE
10.	The programme enables them to be innovative in providing adequate instructional resources for the class and students.	300	75	25	-	-	94	0.1	4.8	VHE
11.	Academic staff are able to manipulate some of the school equipment such as the computer during and after collaboration studies.	200	100	50	30	20	85	0.2	4.2	HE
12.	The non-availability of enough funds to provide technological equipment for practical oriented, learning during collaboration studies is a constraint to the influence it has on academic staff.	150	200	30	20	-	82	0.3	4.1	HE

From table 3: shows that raw score of academic staff on the extent to which various level of collaboration studies contributes to their job performance. Based on the decision level, it is clear that academic staff scored 90 and 94 percent respectively as vary High Extent on items 9 and 10, with means of 4.5 and 4.8, while items 11 and 12 record 85 and 82 percent with means scores of 2 and 1. This indicates that academic staff perceived that extent to which collaboration studies contributes to their job performance in tertiary institutions was high.

Hypothesis 1: There is no Significant Relationship between Distant Learning and Job Performance of Academic Staff in Tertiary Institutions.

Table 4: Relationship between Distant Learning and Job Performance of Academic Staff in Tertiary Institutions

Variables	N	df (N-2)	\bar{X}	Stand Dev.	t-Cal	t-Crit	Sig level	Decision
Distant learning programme	400	398	4.502	0.19	11.8168	1.960	0.05	Rejected
Academic staff job performance			4.116	0.25				

The mean and standard deviation of responses about distant learning and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions are in Imo State are presented in Table 4.4 with N = 400, df = 398 and Q = 0.05 the t-calculated value of 11.8168 establishes a positive relationship between the two variable since it is greater than the critical value of t-(1.960) therefore hypotheses one is thus not accepted and the conclusion is that, there is a significant relationship between distant learning programme and academic staff job performance in tertiary institution in Imo State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no Significant Relationship between Availability of Workshops Job Performance of Academic Staff in Tertiary Institutions.

Table 5: Relationship between Availability of Workshop and Job Performance of Academic Staff in Tertiary Institutions

Variables	N	df (N-2)	\bar{X}	Stand Dev.	t-Cal	t-Crit	Sig level	Decision
Availability of workshops	400	398	4.101	0.321	12.341	1.960	0.05	Rejected
Academic staff job performance			4.310	0.301				

Table 5 present the means and standard deviation scores of the responses about availability of workshops and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Imo State. With N = 400, df = 398 and Q = 0.05. However, the calculated value of t-statistic between workshops and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions are (12.341) while, the critical value of t- are (1.960) respectively. To this end, the t-calculated show a positive relationship between the two variable since it is greater than the critical value. Therefore, hypothesis two is not accepted and the conclusion is that, there is a significant relationship between workshops and job performance of academic staff in Tertiary Institutions in Imo State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no Significant Relationship between Collaborations studies and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institution.

Table 6: Relationship between Collaboration Studies and Job Performance of Academic Staff in Tertiary Institutions

Variables	N	df (N-2)	\bar{X}	Stand Dev.	t-Cal	t-Crit	Sig level	Decision
Collaboration Studies	400	398	4.521	0.159	16.036	1.960	0.05	Rejected
Academic staff job performance			4.201	0.231				

Table 6: Presents the means and standard deviation scores of the responses about collaboration studies and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Imo State. With $N= 4000$, $df = 398$ and $Q - 0.05$, the calculated t-value of (16.036) shows a positive relationship between the two variables since. It is greater than the t-critical value of (1.960). This implies that Hypothesis three is not accepted and of course of conclusion is that, is a significant relationship between collaboration studies and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institution in Imo State.

Discussion of Findings

The result in this research area showed that distant learning as a capacity building programme actually influence the job performance of academic staff positively. The study revealed that since 3 and 2 mean value was rated High Extent which mean that the scores were accepted by the respondent. Research question two was on workshop as another capacity building programme that also influence the job performance of academic staff positively with items 7 and 8 record 80% and 83% respectively with 3 and 1. By then- scores they expressed High Extent. Furthermore, research three shows the extent to which collaboration studies contributes positively to the job performance of academic staff in tertiary institution. It is clear that academic staff scored 90 and 94 percent respectively shows Very High Extent on items 9 and 10; with means score of 4.5 and 4.8. This implies that academic staff perceived the extent to which collaboration studies contributes to their job performance in their profession was high. Result of test of the hypotheses had strong indication on the total outcomes of the three research hypotheses in all, the hypotheses tested were all rejected. This shows that there is a significant relationship between the distant learning, workshops, collaboration studies and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institution in Imo State.

CONCLUSION

Based on the finding, the research concludes that there is significant relationship between distant learning and job performance of academic staff. There is also significant relationship between workshops and job performance of academic staff. There is significant relationship between collaboration studies and job performance of academic staff in tertiary institutions. With the high transformation values gotten in all the test hypotheses from $Ho_1 - Ho_2$ the strength of all the relationship are very high.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of this research study, the researcher discovered that there is no well defined order or organized way of capacity building programme for academic staff in tertiary institutions in Imo State. While some that are in good relationship with the institution administration are constantly nominated or delegated for one capacity building programme or the other, the rest are left at the mercy of their original knowledge and skills. Giving the foregoing, the following recommendations were made:

1. The practice of favoritism should be abolished and training or capacity building programme of all sort distributed equitably according to the need of both the individual(s) and the institutions.
2. Academic staff capacity building must be thought of as a long-term process, which begging with initial preparation and only ends when the academic staff retires from the profession. This new approach to the education and development of academic staff requires a transformation of process and polices that supports academic staff their education their work and their growth in the profession.
3. Academic staff, capacity building must be systematically planned, supported, funded and researched to guarantee the effectiveness of this process.

4. The kinds of capacity building programme and activities designed by and for academic staff must respond to their professional needs, their personal and professional interests.

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